

Mizo Women in Politics and Governance

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Abstract:

In Mizoram, Mizo women vote, seek public office, and join political parties, although their participation is lower than that of men on average. In the last general election to the 40-seat state legislative assembly in 2023, three women were elected from 27 women candidates. In addition to this, the latest general election to the local councils and village councils in 2025 had 5 women candidates being elected from the general seats.

Even though Mizo society is patriarchal in nature, women have historically maintained significant administrative roles while not actively participating. And their influences could not go unnoticed, as the first Chieftain of the Mizo, Zahmuaka, accepted the invitation for the Chieftainship under the influences of his wife, Lawileri. Mizo women were eventually allowed to hold the position of chieftaincy. Though they were mostly the widowed chieftains and regents for their sons, they have played crucial roles in the history of Mizoram.

With the advancement of the Christian missionaries and the establishment of formal educational institutions, the position of women in Mizo society gradually improved. And the provisions in India's 73rd and 106th Amendment Acts further pushed the status of Mizo women to a higher level. However, even with 4,41,559 female voters in Mizoram, there were still very few women participating in politics.

This paper will examine Mizo women in their participation in the traditional male-dominated politics and governance, emphasising the history, transformation, issues, and findings.

Keywords: Chieftainship, assembly house, general seat, voters, transformation, election

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Introduction

Looking back at Mizoram history, women seldom took an active part in the governance and politics. However, their roles in day-to-day life and family well-being were a subject of profound significance. This paper delves into the transformation of Mizo women's participation in politics and governance. It focuses on the dynamic surroundings of Mizo women, highlighting the history, challenges, opportunities, and evolving trends which transformed them from neglected to diligent status in the modern era.

Mizoram, with its patriarchal society, has a long and complex history of gender inequalities. The low status of women in the society got manifested in the male-dominated political sphere. Despite the nation's inclusive constitutional frameworks and its reservation policies for women, Mizo women often need to break down traditional barriers to enter into gender parity in politics at the local level, as well as at the state level.

The 106th Amendment Act, 2023, also known as the Women's Reservation Bill, reserves one-third of seats for women in the Lok Sabha, State Legislative Assemblies, and the Legislative Assembly of the National Capital Territory of Delhi. According to Drishti (2023), the India's 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act, which came into effect in 1993, had already reserved one-third of electoral seats for women in local governance structures in rural and urban areas. Globally, as of 1 January 2025, there are 25 countries where 28 women serve as heads of state and/or government (UN Women, 2025). However, as Kusuma (2024) states, it is important to recognise that the participation of women in politics is not merely a matter of numerical representation but a reflection of a broader struggle for gender equality and social justice. Therefore, this in-depth study will analyse and observe the Mizo women in politics and governance, providing a comprehensive view of the issues and opportunities faced by them.

Historical Background of Mizo Women in Politics and Governance

The origin of the Mizos, like those of many other tribes in northeastern India, is shrouded in mystery. The generally accepted history was that they were a part of the great Mongoloid waves of migration from China and later moved out to India to their present habitat (Ministry of Communication & Information Technology, National Informatics Centre [NIC], Mizoram, n.d.) in the northeastern corner, bordering Myanmar in the east and south and Bangladesh in the western side. Mizo literally means people living in the highland, and before the advent of British government, Mizo tribes lived in an autonomous village having village chiefs in their respective villages. Mizos are now classified as Scheduled Tribes by the

Government of India, giving preferential treatment in the matters of jobs, education, etc., as a means to accelerate their integration into mainstream society. There are many tribal ethnic groups in Mizoram. The major tribes among Mizos are Ralte, Pachuau, Chawngthu, Tlau, Mara, Lai, Paihte, Thahdo, Hmar, Darlong, Chakma, etc. (Protocol & Hospitality Wing, General Administration Department, Government of Mizoram, n.d.)

It is generally believed that the chieftainship was established during their migratory movement in Chin Hills, Myanmar. Zatluanga (1996) discusses the historical development of Mizo society and culture and says when the leader of the Hnamte clan passed away, Hnamte clan invited Zahmuaka to become their chief and rule over them, as they needed care and protection from their enemies. Zahmuaka initially declined their invitation, but the behind-the-scenes talk of his wife Lawileri – who said, “If we, the humblest of all people, are invited, it is right to accept their request.” changed his mind and accepted their invitation, becoming the first chieftain of the Mizo people (Lalfakawmi, 2019).

Even though the first chieftaincy was established under the influence of a woman, women in Mizo society seldom played significant roles in the administration and governance. The chief performed all the administrative, legislative and judicial functions in the village with the help

of a council of male elders called Khawnbawl Upa. Their status in the society soared only if their husbands were village chiefs, Thangchhuahpa or Pasaltha who were great hunters, or Khuangchawipa who possessed great wealth. However, Lalrinchhani (n.d.) examines the socio-economic conditions of early Mizo society from a gender perspective, and states there were no privileges for the women to achieve higher social status to surpass their male counterparts, and they had never got a chance to participate in village administration.

The chieftaincy of the Mizos later became hereditary, though it was also fought for in certain cases so as to expand their influences to neighbouring villages. Colbert (2010) provides an in-depth analysis of women’s political engagement in Mizoram. According to her, when Sentlang village chieftain Lalngura died in 1855, his wife Lalhlupuii reigned as regent as their son Vanpuilala was about 4 or 5 years of age . She became the first woman to reign as Chieftainess, and she was followed by Darbilhi of Darzo village, who became the chieftainess of Darzo village after her husband passed away.

During the ‘Chin-Lushai Expedition of 1889-1890’, Darbilhi, the chieftainess of Darzo village, instead of fighting with the British, made friendship with J. Shakespear, the Field Intelligence Officer of the Chittagong Column, (Explore Mizoram, 2022) and Colbert (2010) says Darbilhi made J. Shakespear his

blood brother. According to Department of History, Hnahthial Government College (2019), a fort known as the “Fort Tregear” was established at Darzo Hill on 4th March 1890, and Darzo became one of the centres of colonial rule in Mizoram, then Lushai Hills.

Another prominent Mizo chieftainess was Ropuiliani, remembered as one of the most courageous figures in Mizoram for her resistance against British aggression. The Department of History, Hnahthial Government College (2015) highlights Ropuiliani’s leadership and resistance against colonial forces. Ropuiliani assumed the position of chieftainess of Denlung village in 1889 following the death of her husband, Vandula, who was regarded as the most eminent chief of the South Lushai Hills. Ropuiliani symbolised bravery and selflessness during the Indian freedom struggle. According to Amrit Mahotsav (2023), Lalnu Ropuiliani exemplified bravery in resisting British colonial influence in Mizoram. She refused to recognise British colonial rule because she did not believe that the British colonists were superior, and as a result, she was imprisoned by the imperialists in 1893. She was taken to a jail in Rangamati, Undivided India, after being first imprisoned in Lunglei, Mizoram. In January 1894, Chieftainess Ropuiliani died in prison, and she is remembered for her resistance against British colonial forces.

Another chieftainesses who took over the chieftaincy after their husbands died were Suaki of Hnahchang village (Amrit Mahotsav 2023), Darsuakpuii of Thiltlang village, Sangkungi of Chalkai village, (Lalthangliana B. 2001), Darhnuni of Thiltlang village, Sumkungi of Hlumte village, Rothangpuii of Mathtlang village (Colbert, I. 2010), Dosangi of Tuahzawl village, and Thawmi of Lungleng village (Chhanchhana, personal communication, 2023).

In the eastern part of Mizoram, Neihpuithangi, the wife of the famous Lusei chieftain, Vuttaia of East Lungdar, ruled over two hundred and sixty houses with sixty guns after her husband bequeathed a part of his estate. She took active part in the Eastern Lushai Raising in 1893 – 1894, and opposed the imperialists during Chin Lushai Expedition 1889 – 1890 under General Tregear. And, according to Chatterjee S. (1990), she was severely punished by the English.

Besides the famous and patriotic Mizo chieftainess mentioned above, Pakunga Rani (Pakunga’s wife) became chieftainess after her husband died, and became the ally of the British. She helped the English during Lushai Expedition 1871 – 1872. As a result, the eastern Lushais under the chieftains Lungliana, Nikhama and Zakhrawka raided her village, and she was brutally murdered in 13th December, 1888 near Tlabung, the then Demagiri (Elly 1978).

Another chieftainess to be noted is Buki, who became chieftainess of Durtlang as her husband could not pay her bride price, and bequeathed a part of his estate which she ruled over as an independent chieftainess. She outwardly retained friendship with the local authorities of Cachar, but not a British ally like Pakunga Rani. When she died in 28th July, 1887, she was succeeded by her daughter – Vanhnuaitangi.

However, apart from the few mentioned chieftainesses, Mizo women did not have significant roles in the village administration and social organisations.

Mizo Women in Post-Independent Era.

Mizoram was declared as part of the British-India by a proclamation in 1895 (Government of Mizoram, n.d.). The British acknowledged the traditional chieftains and chieftainesses as the local leaders and governing intermediaries. Under the Government of India Act 1935, certain areas in Assam and the North East Frontier tracts had been designated as Excluded or Partially Excluded Areas. Accordingly, the Sub-Committee was appointed on 27 February 1947 by the Advisory Committee on Fundamental Rights, Minorities and Tribal and Excluded Areas, known as the Bordoloi Sub-committee, which visited the then Lushai Hills in 1947 (Constitution of India n.d.). A certain degree of autonomy was approved by the government and included in the Sixth Schedule of the Constitution as a result of the Bordoloi Sub-Committee's recommendation. Following the establishment of these organisations and the creation of the Lushai Hills Autonomous District Council in 1952, chieftainship was abolished in Mizo society.

Many writers and scholars state that the status of women in Mizo society is never high. However, it is noteworthy that when the District Conference of Lushai Hills was held in 16th April 1947, five persons were appointed to speak to the Bordoloi Sub-committee who visited Mizoram, and one woman, Lalziki was included among them. And, when the Bordoloi Sub-committee left, the District Conference appointed a 9-person sub-committee to look to the rules for administration of Mizoram, which included another one woman – Zami, President of Women's Union (Colbert, I. 2010).

In addition to this, when the Lushai Hills District Council was about to be established, Advisory Council was formed beforehand, which consisted of 35 members (Zorema J. 2007), including 2 women representatives – Lalsangpuii from Aizawl and Remthangi of Lunglei. However, when Lushai chief delegates were chosen in 1940, no female chiefs were included, and the District Conferences in 1946 and 1947 did not include any females among the 20 commoners and 10 Lushai chieftains that were chosen.

(1) Women in General Elections to the Mizo District Council

In the first election to the Mizo District Council in 1952, though one female member, Lalziki, occupied the nominated seat, there was no woman among the 18 elected members (Nag 1999). The outcome of the second election in 1957 was the same: 24 male members were elected, but no female members were chosen aside from Hmingliani, the only female member who sat in the nominated seat. No women were among the 22 elected members and the two nominated members at the third election held in 1962. Mizo women, again, did not receive representation in either the elected or nominated seats in the fourth and last election held in 1972 (Vanlawma, R. 1969).

Additionally, the Assam Legislative Assembly always had male representatives of the Mizo District Council. Three male candidates from the Mizo District Council were elected to the Assam Legislative Assembly in the general election of 1957; the same outcome was obtained in the elections of 1962 and 1967, with no women representatives (Election Commission of India n.d).

(2) Women in General Elections to the Legislative Assembly

In the 1972 Mizoram legislative assembly's first general election, after Mizoram became a Union Territory, four women filed for candidatures, but male candidates won every assembly constituency, and Saptawni was inducted in the nominated seat. Nevertheless, one woman, Thanmawii, filed for a candidature in the 1978 general election, and she won the Serchhip assembly constituency, becoming the first woman legislator in Mizoram. The 1979 general election witnessed 3 women candidates, but only one of them, Thanmawii from the Aizawl East constituency, got elected to the assembly, and K Thansiami was included in the nominated seat. However, the 1984 general election to the legislative assembly did not have any woman candidates, and Rokungi was inducted in the nominated seat.

After Mizoram became a state in 1987, the first general election to the state assembly was held in 1987. And there were four female candidates in 40 assembly constituencies; one of them, Lalhlimpuii from Aizawl North-1, was elected to the state assembly. And Lalhlimpuii was inducted into the ministry as a minister of state, becoming the first Mizo woman to hold the position of minister. The 1989 general election also had four female candidates; however, male candidates won every assembly constituency. The same result appeared in the 1993 general election; all the three female candidates were defeated by their male counterparts. The 1998 general election was another adversity for Mizo women, as all the 10 female candidates were prevailed over by male candidates. Seven women contested again in the 2003 general

election, but they were again defeated. The 2008 general election also witnessed 9-woman candidates defeated, and another 6-woman candidates were won against in the 2013 general election. Another 15 female candidates in the 2018 general election were also again prevailed over by their counterparts.

However, despite the fact that women were consistently defeated in the previous seven state assembly general elections, 16 female candidates faced the 2023 general election, and three of them were elected (Election Commission of India n.d). Thus, three decades of women's recurring failures to sit in the state assembly came to an end when the three women—Baryl Vanneihsang from Aizawl South-III, Lalrinpui from Lunglei East, and Prova Chakma from West Tuipui—became Members of the Legislative Assembly. And Lalrinpui from the Lunglei East Assembly constituency was inducted as the first female cabinet minister of Mizoram.

Years of Election	No's of Women Voters	No's of Women Candidates Contested	No's of Women Candidates Elected
1972	80,583	4	0
1978	1,11,982	1	1
1979	1,20,259	3	1
1984	3,065	0	0
1987	1,53,634	4	1
1989	1,65,163	4	0
1993	1,99,683	3	0
1998	2,22,104	10	0
2003	2,67,518	7	0
2008	3,09,129	9	0
2013	3,50,333	6	0
2018	3,94,939	15	0
2023	4,38,578	16	3

Number of women contested and elected in Mizoram legislative assembly

(Election Commission of India n.d).

Compared to the male members of the current Mizoram State Legislative Assembly, the three female members are a relatively small number. According to Chief Electoral Officer, Mizoram, n.d., in 2025, female voters make up 4,41,520 of the 8,56,297 electors in total, with 4,14,777 being male voters. Even though

Mizo women's status is improving and many positive changes are visible, just 7.5% of the seats in the present state legislature are occupied by female members.

(3) Women in General Elections to the Local Councils & Village Councils

After chieftaincy was abolished, the District Council and village councils assumed the responsibilities of the chiefs. The village council, whose members are elected by the villagers, governs each village, and women rarely have the opportunity to join. Gangte (2011) states women did not have political status and their role was confined to domestic activities. In addition, Mercie G. (2010) says, the Mizo women, like the other women belonging to different tribes in northeast region of India, do not have any formal laws recognizing and protecting their rights. The patriarchal nature of Mizo society might have been the reason for women for not having voices in the village administration in early days. And, Lalthansangi (2005) argued that the contributions of Mizo women were usually neglected or relegated to the background and the whole history of politics and chieftainship, village administration etc., were male-centred.

The first election to the village councils held in 1954 had only 2 female council members from 338 village councils. And, the 1957 and the 1960 elections to the 381 village councils did not have any woman members. In the 1963 and 1975 elections, only one woman each got elected from 422 village councils. The 1982 election had two women got elected and there were no women in 1983 election. In 1984, 6 women were elected from 412 village councils, the 1987 election had 4, the 1988 by-election witnessed 3 women elected from 16 village councils. In 1990, another 3 women were elected, 23 women were elected in 1994, in 1997 election 15 women were elected. However, in 2002 general election the Village Council, 48 female candidates were elected to 532 village councils, and two of them were chosen to serve as council presidents (Lalhmingpuii & Namchoom, 2014), indicating that women's role is progressively changing. According to the Mizoram State Election Commission (2009), the general election to the Village Council in 2009 had 82 women candidates in 555 village councils, and 31 of them were elected. In the 2012 First General Election to the Local Council for 82 Local Councils within Aizawl Municipality, out of 522 seats, 26 women were elected (Mizoram State Election Commission, n.d.).

Mizoram adopted the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act on 24th April 2019 by passing the Mizoram Panchayati Raj (Amendment) Act, 2019. Accordingly, there were seats reserved for women in the Local Councils and Village Councils. And, the general elections to the Local and Village Councils since 2020 had reserved seats for women which greatly decreases the political marginalisation of women in local and village administrations.

However, in the general election for local councils in 2025, besides 195 separate reserved seats for women, out of 528 general seats, only two women—R. Laltnanmawii of Muanna Veng, Aizawl, and C. Lallawmsangi of Salem Veng, Lunglei—were elected from the Aizawl Municipality and the Lunglei Municipal Council, respectively. Women elected in Local Council Elections from general seats in 2025 were a mere 0.37%.

In the general election for village councils in 2025, there were 613 reserved seats for women and 1803 general seats. Besides the reserved seats, only three women - CL Thangi, Dinthar, Champhai District; R Lalhmingliani, Zotlang East, Champhai District; and Zonunvuli, North Sabual, Mamit District were elected from the general seat, and women candidates elected from the general seat is only 0.16%. Hence, in the 2025 general elections for local and village councils, only 5 women were elected from 2331 general seats, in addition to the 808 women who were elected from reserved seats for women. Thus, Mizo women occupied 25.89% of seats in the present local councils and village councils.

(4) Women in General Elections to House of the People (Lok Sabha) and Rajya Sabha

Mizoram has a single constituency to the Lok Sabha, and the Rajya Sabha. The first election to the Lok Sabha was held in 1972, the latest in 2024. There were just three female candidates between 1972 and 2024: Rita Malsawmi in 2024, Lalthlamuani in 2019, and K Sanglianchhungi in 1977. However, all of them were, unfortunately, prevailed over by their male counterparts (Chief Electoral Officer Mizoram 2024). According to the Government of Mizoram (n.d.), the 6 members, including the former members and present member in the Rajya Sabha from 1972 to 2025 are all male legislators.

Issues face by Mizo Women in Politics and Governance

Even though Mizo women participated in politics and governance since pre-independent periods, their roles have been marginalised and mostly confined to tight spaces with few exceptions in pre-independent era. They have many issues that hinder their engagement in politics. Many traditional, cultural, social, and political elements influence the problems Mizo women encounter in politics and government. Although there has been some improvement steadily, Mizo women still encounter obstacles that prevent them from fully participating and being represented in governmental decision-making processes.

The issues face by Mizo women in politics and governance may be sum up as follows:

1. **Cultural and Traditional Problems:** The patriarchal nature of Mizo society prevents women from taking active part in politics and governance. In a male dominated environment, their roles have been relegated to domestic duties. And, Social pressure frequently pushes Mizo women to put their family and home duties ahead of their own professional advancement.

Moreover, the traditional chieftaincy consisted mostly of male chieftains, and the long-held notion that men should handle administrative matters is still in place.

2. **Economic Barrier:** Economic independence is still a challenge for many Mizo women due to the patriarchal society of the Mizos. Their capacity to engage in political processes is impacted since they do not have the funds necessary for political engagement by their own.
3. **Gender Disparity in Political Parties:** Political parties in Mizoram have limited focus on promotion of gender equality. There was a gap between male and female members as a result of the creation of women's wings or fronts in several political parties. They were degenerated to play supporting roles in their parties' secondary branches rather than making decisions in the main branches. They are often seen as support figures for male politicians, and different political parties in Mizoram never have women leaders till date.
4. **Information Gap:** Even though Mizo women have a higher level of education than women in other parts of India, there is still a lack of political socialisation. Many of them are not aware of their political rights, that hinders them from taking active part in governance.
5. **Quota and Reservation:** Even though quota and reservation are made for the upliftment of women, it may lead to tokenism. In the last general election to the village councils and local councils' elections in 2025, besides 808 reserved seats for women, only 5 female candidates were elected from general seats.
6. **Ideology of Mizo Christians:** A significant barrier to Mizo women's political engagement was the misinterpretation of biblical teachings that supported patriarchy. And, the patriarchal nature of Mizo society has permeated Christian communities, where the male-dominated church reflects the male-dominated society, notwithstanding the immense changes Christianity brought to Mizo society, particularly in the advancement of women. They are still excluded from various decision-making bodies, ordination and other responsible positions.

Findings and Conclusion

Even though the political participation of Mizo women is increasing steadily, their roles are still marginalised in governance. Besides a handful chieftainess in early days, Mizoram never have a woman leader who plays important roles in politics and governance.

During 1952 to 1972, when Mizoram was included in Assam as a separate district, the Mizo District Council had only two female members, who were inducted in the nominated seats. And, there were no female members elected from Mizoram to the Assam Legislative Assembly during 1957 to 1967. Additionally, there was only one Minister of State, and one Cabinet Minister among the five female members of the Mizoram Legislative Assembly, who were elected in general elections held between 1972 and 2023.

From 1954 to till 2025 general elections to the Village Councils, women candidates elected were far more less than male. The same results are seen in the general elections to the local councils held between 2012 and 2025. Besides the reserved seats allocated for women, only 5 women were elected from the general seats in the latest local and village council elections.

Moreover, Mizoram parliamentary constituency never had a woman representative, in either the Lok Sabha or the Rajya Sabha, till date.

The above findings show how Mizo women were marginalised in the field of politics and governance. The current politics and governance are virtually controlled by men. Cultural and traditional problems, including patriarchy are the main issues faced by them. Economic dependency is another challenge Mizo women have been facing, and gender disparity in political parties further prevents them from taking active roles in politics. The information gap, quotas and reservations, and the ideology of church members in the Christian-dominated state of Mizoram that keeps up the patriarchal nature of society are also proving to cause hindrances to Mizo women in their political participation.

Therefore, it is necessary to improve political socialisation to develop political knowledge, values, and ideology, in order to overcome these problems. Despite having an 89.27 percent literacy rate (Census2011.co.in, n.d.), the majority of Mizo women are unaware of their political rights. Their economic status needs to be improved, and they need to be more involved in political parties, NGOs, and religious institutions. They should do more than just run their own separate associations, wings, fronts, or fellowships etc.

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